

Master Thesis Evaluation Frames Overview

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Comparison of different methods for illumination calculation using Light Probes in virtual worlds with respect to their influence on plausibility for AR applications

In this document all captured frames for the evaluation of different light probe placement approaches are collected in one document. The simultaneous frames for each approach are listed opposite each other. This ensures a good overview of the differences between the approaches.

(a) Indoor

(b) Cornell Box

(c) Outdoor

1 Indoor Frames

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 2: Indoor Frames 0001

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 3: Indoor Frames 0002

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 4: Indoor Frames 0003

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 5: Indoor Frames 0004

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 6: Indoor Frames 0005

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 7: Indoor Frames 0006

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 8: Indoor Frames 0007

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 9: Indoor Frames 0008

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 10: Indoor Frames 0009

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 11: Indoor Frames 0010

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 12: Indoor Frames 0011

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 13: Indoor Frames 0012

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 14: Indoor Frames 0013

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 15: Indoor Frames 0014

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 16: Indoor Frames 0015

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 17: Indoor Frames 0016

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 18: Indoor Frames 0017

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 19: Indoor Frames 0018

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 20: Indoor Frames 0019

2 Cornell Frames

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 21: Cornell Frames 0001

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 22: Cornell Frames 0002

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 23: Cornell Frames 0003

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 24: Cornell Frames 0004

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 25: Cornell Frames 0005

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 26: Cornell Frames 0006

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 27: Cornell Frames 0007

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 28: Cornell Frames 0008

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 29: Cornell Frames 0009

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 30: Cornell Frames 0010

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 31: Cornell Frames 0011

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 32: Cornell Frames 0012

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 33: Cornell Frames 0013

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 34: Cornell Frames 0014

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 35: Cornell Frames 0015

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 36: Cornell Frames 0016

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 37: Cornell Frames 0017

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 38: Cornell Frames 0018

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 39: Cornell Frames 0019

3 Outdoor Frames

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 40: Outdoor Frames 0001

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 41: Outdoor Frames 0002

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 42: Outdoor Frames 0003

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 43: Outdoor Frames 0004

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 44: Outdoor Frames 0005

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 45: Outdoor Frames 0006

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 46: Outdoor Frames 0007

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 47: Outdoor Frames 0008

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 48: Outdoor Frames 0009

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 49: Outdoor Frames 0010

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 50: Outdoor Frames 0011

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 51: Outdoor Frames 0012

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 52: Outdoor Frames 0013

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 53: Outdoor Frames 0014

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 54: Outdoor Frames 0015

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 55: Outdoor Frames 0016

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 56: Outdoor Frames 0017

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 57: Outdoor Frames 0018

(a) Ground Truth

(b) Geometrical-driven

(c) Illumination-driven

(d) Grid placement

(e) One Probe

(f) Real Time positioning

(g) Mask

Figure 58: Outdoor Frames 0019